

" The ways education institutions can promote change referring to the models of change with
AI generators. "

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Introduction

This literature review explores how educational institutions can effectively implement change by utilizing established change models, with a particular focus on the integration of AI-driven technologies. In the fast-changing educational landscape, institutions must adapt to new teaching methods, technological innovations, and the varied needs of students. Effective change management is essential for these institutions to remain competitive, enhance educational outcomes, and meet the challenges of 21st-century learning. Kotter's Change Model on the Structure of Change, Lewin's Change Management Model, as well as Fullan's Change Theory grab the importance of having structures of change to support change to take place throughout the educational systems. Kotter (1996) along with Fullan (2008) stated that such models offer ideas about how to deal with resistance, engender cooperation, and maintain change in a systematic way, thus, making two such models a valuable possession for leaders in education. For instance, Lewin's model is a three-stage model of 'unfreezing – changing – refrasing', which helps in planning for change, through and consolidating new behaviour within the organisation (Lewin, 1951). Conversely, Kotter's model emphasizes the importance of creating urgency, building coalitions, and enabling action, which can be particularly effective in large-scale educational reforms (Kotter, 1996). Moreover, the incorporation of AI-driven technologies offers new possibilities to enhance these models by delivering data-driven insights, automating routine tasks, and personalizing learning experiences (Ouyang et al., 2023; Bozkurt et al., 2023). AI can catalyse educational change through increasing administrative effectiveness, instant feedback and interactive flexible

learning experiences adapted to each student 's need (UNESCO, 2020). However, it is necessary to further analyse how the traditional change models can be better applied to the field of AI integration.

Research Questions:

The following research questions will guide this literature review, focusing on how educational institutions can effectively foster organizational change by utilizing established change models while integrating AI-driven technologies.

- What strategies are most suitable for educational management to ensure that organisational change can be developed using different change management models such as Kotter's, Lewin's, Fullan, etc. together with AI technologies?
- How can change be supported by the analyzed AI-Dr. technologies in educational institutions, and which model or innovative tools are suitable for this purpose?
- What is known at present regarding the application of AI and innovations in the field of educational transformations and has some sort of educational institutions, such as K-12, higher education institutions made more effective use of artificial intelligence?

- How have change models been modified to include AI and technological innovations in educational contexts, and what are the advantages and disadvantages of using AI to implement these change models?
- Are there areas related to the integration of AI and other innovations in education that remain under-explored, and what challenges do educational institutions encounter when adopting AI-driven change? How can these challenges be addressed?

These questions are intended to situate generic change theories in the contemporary unpredictable role of AI in teaching and learning processes. Answering these questions, this review aims to critically discuss the existing best practices, describe advantages and disadvantages of AI integration into change processes, and outline the directions for further research and practical application.

Literature Review

The literature review will examine the ways in which educational institutions can facilitate change by drawing on process models of change while incorporating technologies that employ AI. This section is divided into several sub-sections in which main aspects of change management and the role of AI in learning environment are discussed. View on the Change in Education itself Change is a vital component within the framework of educational development, stimulated by changes within the society, involution of technologies, as well as changes in policy (Fullan, 2007). In learning entities, they have to adapt their practices in many areas because of diverse students' needs and also improve the kind of teaching practices and available technology. In this sub-section, the main focus is the issues associated with change in education institutions, including; increased change resistance, inadequate resources, and especially the need for adequate change communication in the process of implementing change (Kotter, 1996; Lewin 1951). The fundamental theories for change process in education sector.

- Lewin's Change Management Model: Lewin's first model back to the simplest one consists of three steps in a cycle known as "Unfreeze," "Change," and "Refreeze" where the previously set behaviour is altered, new mind-set and behaviour is implemented and new standards are set up (Lewin, 1951). From this model, it is appreciable to notice the organization readiness for change, the process of change and change that is continuous (BMC Software, 2019; Trowsdale, 2021).

- Kotter's 8-Step Model: Kotter defines a more specific model as having eight distinct stages: creating urgency, assembling the coalition, developing the vision, communicating the vision and managing change, empowering change, creating short term wins, driving sustainability, and instituting change (Kotter, 1996). What is more important to note concerning this model is that leadership, communication and delegation are key to change success (MindTools, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2024).

Figure 1: Kotter's 8-Step Model.

- Fullan's Change Theory recognises the complexity of change processes in the context of education and describes a complex change process which should include the culture, practices and beliefs of the educational setting (Fullan, 2007).. He underlined the need of constant education of all participants involved, cooperation and engagement of all parties interested in knowledge processes.

- **Comparative Analysis:** This section will assess the strengths and weakness of these models particularly in education settings. It will discuss how each model addresses some critical activities this include It will also describe how each model addresses important components including;

Integration of AI in Change Models:

- **Role of AI in Education:** Introducing AI technologies along with change models is beneficial because of a collection of big data, automating the administrative process, and personalizing learning outcomes (UNESCO, 2020). For instance, the student performance data sets can be assessed by the AI tools and hence identify the learning issues which will enable the instructor to modify the learning approaches (Wang, 2022).
- **AI-Enhanced Change Management:** This section will discuss how it is possible to apply transform models that apply AI technologies. In addition, it will analyse case studies and literature that reflect how AI can help with various aspects of change, including monitoring, anticipating obstacles, and promoting the dialogue across stakeholders (Kahn, 2024; Nieto-Rodriguez and Vargas, n.d.; Perifanis and Kitsios, 2023).
- **Challenges and Considerations:** Challenges such as; data privacy, digital divide and pushback against use of new technologies need to be met if there is to be effective use

of the approach (UNESCO, 2020). These challenges will be discussed in this section, and possible solutions for them will be given. A comparative analysis will be used in this article together with debates between proponents of various possible research approaches.

- **Adaptability of Change Models:** The literature review presents the modification of traditional change management models applied in modern learning contexts including the influence of AI. Kotter (1996) and Fullan (2007) have noted that there are two main criticisms of such models: some of them are too rigid and fixed while others argue that the models' very structuring can actually be useful if only they are adapted. This section will discuss these talks and use them to provide a guideline for modifying these models to fit technological developments.
- **Strengths and Limitations of AI Integration:** AI has numerous benefits with it, but like each great tool, it includes a drawback also. To accommodate both the advantages and disadvantages of AI, this section will highlight benefits of AI including better data analysis and efficiency that will be paid for alongside the drawbacks, which are ethical considerations and the need for extensive capital investment (Wang, 2022; UNESCO, 2020).

Gaps in the Literature:

While there has been growing concerns made by scholars to apply AI in education, literature review has shown that there is little research done on how AI technologies can best be integrated into traditional change models.. Many of the recent articles are centered on either change management activities or use of AI, but few look at the possibilities of integrating both in an organization. Furthermore, most of the related works are centering the K-12 and high education organizations while the K-12 and postsecondary organizations are the most common contexts for AI enactment. This sub-section will uncover such gaps and point to the future research direction (Almarashdeh, 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Luckin, 2018).

Successful Case Studies:

- **Examples of Effective Change Initiatives:** This sub-section will give simple examples of how the institutions of learning have implemented change models while moving to AI enagerled technologies. It will also explain the leadership, stakeholder and planning processes that underpinned these accomplishments (UNESCO, 2020; Wang, 2022).
- **Lessons Learned:** Last of all, based on these case studies, the analysis will present some conclusions which will also contain some recommendations for the educational leaders for further optimum functioning in the utilisation of such programmes.

Findings from the Literature Review

1. Models of Change in Education:

The review identified several models of change which are mostly employed in educational settings as vocalized in the article under discussion. It must be noted that each of these models contain different frameworks and approaches for managing change.

1.1 Lewin's Change Management Model:

Kurt Lewin's model, which includes three stages: WHO are these key players in the process of unfreezing, changing, and refreezing, and how does the learning organisation relate to the field of education? As a result of various researchers, the unfreezing process that aimed at increasing the awareness of the need to change seems to be crucial in addressing the potential organizational resistance from individuals who are involved in the process such as the teachers as well as the parents. This model has been adopted by educators in addressing curriculum reforms ad instructional strategies. For instance, in a study conducted by Hargreaves (2018) identified that schools which engaged the teachers at the early stage in the unfreezing process sought higher level of commitments and flexibility as the other change phases ensue.

Figure 2: Kurt Lewin's model.

1.2 Kotter's 8-Step Change Model:

This means that Kotter's model supports the kind of integrated, phased process to power implementation. Each from the steps, starting from creating urgency to the establishment of new approaches as cultural norms has been found useful in educational leadership settings. (Dang, Nguyễn, 2024) proved that schools implementing Kotter's model in reform movements enjoy better results in students' learning and performances. An example is a study in one district that investigated the general adoption of technology in all schools: School principals and leaders used the eight steps Kotter pointed out to build the sense of the need and the buy-in from educators (Saifaldin, Idris, and Onia, 2022; Appelbaum et al., 2012).

Figure 3: Kotter's 8-Step Change Model.

1.3 Fullan's Change Theory:

According to Fullan's Change Theory, educational change is detailed, and should therefore be approached holistically and comprehensively, while paying attention to the culture, practice and other attitudes prevailing in any given learning institutions. In this capacity, Fullan (2007) pointed that change cannot be made in isolation and thus, should involve systematic approach that integrates these strategies in achieve sustainable change. His theory also underscores the importance of formation of education capacity which will assist the educators and institutions to adapt to the changing Guatemala education. Furthermore, Fullan raises the issues of participation, where the teachers, principals, learners, school adopting the change, and the community are all participants in the change. This approach also promotes ownership within the respective teams improving the likelihood of implementation. Consequently, Fullan's model is useful in establishing ongoing participation so that institutions build an environment that fosters alterations in the long run, making the model suitable for any attempt to pursue educational improvements (Meister, 2000; Cochren, 1995; Noguera, 2006).

— Fullan, 2008a

Figure 4.

2. Contemplated Change Strategies and Practices:

The literature review also found that change implementation in educational contexts requires particular methods and approaches.

2.1 Collaborative Leadership:

Shared leadership surfaced as one of the most comprehensive themes revealed in the numerous reviewed researches. According to Li (2023), warm-urged environment leadership is more effective concerning change management. Overall, the results of the implementation of shared-decision making and participatory governance were improved teacher morale, satisfaction, and commitment necessary for institutional change. For example, an evaluation of transformation process in secondary school reveal that the teachers should be included when deciding on changes to be made to the curriculum because this help in enhancing the implementation process (Magnasofa and Najib, 2019; Kalinovich and Marrone, 2017).

2.2 Professional Development:

This paper supports the idea of continuous professional learning as key to change in the practices of education. Various researches show that the best approach strategy is the individualized engagements in Professional Development that meet the context and requirement of the teaching force which leads to a better process in the concept correspondence in the professional development process of the educator. For instance, (Dahl et al., 2023) conducted a study and realized that schools that put a lot of effort to enhance trusting professional development practices were rewarded with increased improvements in their

instructional practices. Since training was positioned accordingly to the aspects of the chosen change model, the educators were able to address new expectations and approaches (Dahl et al., 2023; Муканова et al., 2023; Guskey, 1994).

2.3 Data-Driven Decision Making:

Another important practice considered in the literature is data-driven decision-making. Applying data accomplishes this by providing educational leaders with insight into the effectiveness of change interventions and useful strategies to implement changes. Khan. (2024) have noted that schools using student data to make appropriate decisions benefited from better student performance and program success. In this way, formative assessments adopted by educators as well as feedback mechanisms could have shown progress and help with decision making (Neria, 2024; Bai, 2024; Asfaw et al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2024; Khan, 2024).

3. Barriers to Change

The literature reveals a number of challenges that barriers that educational institutions experience when implementing change.

3.1 Resistance to Change:

Stakeholder resistance is one of the greatest barriers to change implementation among organizations. Findings point to a common tendency for stakeholders

to resent changes stemming from reported self-organizing risks such as threats arising out unknown territories or risks to pre-set roles. For example, in Vurayai (2024) point out that as a result of understanding Negative Aspects Should Be Addressed Early it is crucial to solve controversy or misunderstanding with the change process in order to have less resistance. From the findings of the study, the level of success that schools achieved in mitigating the stubbornness was determined by the extent to which the schools had effectively communicated and involved other stakeholders in the planning phase ('Addressing resistance to change through a micro interpersonal lens', 2022; Vurayai, 2024; Butler et al., 2002; Córca, 2020).

3.2 Insufficient Resources:

Some of the challenges that have come up with include the following: capacity constraints in the form of funds, time, and people. This study by Barrios (2022) reveals that most organisations have many challenges in implementing change, including insufficient funding for sustaining change efforts in learning institutions. Another finding was that facilities that sought extra source of revenue to support change and or engaged in funding collaborations were more likely to show enhanced adoption and sustainment of change. For example, existing collaborations with local merchants and communities provided organisational demand in technological acquirement initiatives (Barrios, 2022; Siddiqi et al., 2022; Petersson and Ingemarsson, 2014; Lauer, 2021).

3.3 Lack of Clear Vision:

Without a specific vision of the changes, different stakeholders in institutions may not be on the same page. According to researches, there is likelihood for a change process to be successful if there are visions and goals in an institution. According to Walters (2012), the role learning leaders have to present a clear vision that maintains and mobilises others to the aim. The level of engagement /commitment among educators was determined by the extent to which the schools had articulated a vision on change (Venus et al., 2019; McCown, 1995; Walters, 2012).

4. The Role of Technology in Change

Technology theme has been evident in the literature due to the fact it has changed the face of education institutions.

4.1 The use of technology as a driver of change is the first.

In many cases, technology is recognized as a leading agent that catalyses change in learning spaces. Guided by prior research, the teachers come to find that the integration of technology promotes the development of creative approaches in teaching and can also increase the learners' engagement. For example, Coelho and Cabrita (2016) says that integration of fully face-to-face classroom and technology-mediated learning spaces, as described by the blended learning concept, has led to improvement in students' performance. Change agents that ensured that technology formed part of their change initiatives confessed to higher rates of success in changes such as new curriculum and teaching methods (Coelho and Cabrita, 2016; Avidov-Ungar and Eshet-Alkakay, 2011; Pisanu, 2014).

4.2 Professional Learning Communities:

Thus, the creation of the Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) that are learning communities based around the use of technology has been effective. According to Cheng and Robinson (2002), PLC provides teachers with an opportunity to share knowledge of how to integrate use of technology in class. The schools that implemented PLCs focusing on technology provided more innovation and better use of technological goals in teaching and learning process (Cheng and Robinson, 2002; Ahmad Jalaludin et al., 2022; Professional Learning Communities, 2023; Burgstahler and Swift, 1996; Ampanon, 2024).

Implications for Future Change

The educational landscape is changing rapidly due to technological advancements, societal shifts, and the demand for equitable access to quality education. As institutions respond to these changes, it is essential to understand the implications for future change. This section discusses insights drawn from the literature review, emphasizing key areas for educational leaders to concentrate on in order to encourage sustainable and effective change within their institutions.

1. Emphasis on Adaptive Leadership

1.1 Understanding Adaptive Leadership

The future of educational institutions will expect leadership that adapts far better than it has in the past. Adaptive leaders are those who resemble that they are able to work

in changing environment, to respond to emerging threats, and mobilize people for the achievement of goals. According to Heifetz and Laurie (2017), adaptive work entails embracing change and developing strength at the employee and the organisational level.

1.2 Capacity Building for Flexibility

It is imperative that educational leaders and managers should attain personal versatility, self, and staff adaptability. This includes training teachers on such things as adaptive leadership principles and Cult of Repetition, as well as promoting risk-taking across Classroom. Institutions should therefore aim at ensuring that they institute flexible, healthily collaborative, and knowledge solving oriented professions.

2. Is Technology the Key for Change

2.1 A Review of the Role of Technology in Educational Change.

In my perspective, technology will as a matter of fact continue to be the moving force behind educational change. The use of ICT in teaching and learning activities improves learners and instructors' view, course management, and organizational efficiency. As Anderson (2020) observed, technology can be trails as prompting and supporting novel instructions and learning approaches.

2.2 Professional Development in Implementation of Technology.

For technology to be more effective in creating innovative forms of learning and teaching, educators should spend their professional development focusing on the

technology that is available for them to incorporate into teaching and learning process. It is therefore important that teachers should be taught how to apply the technology in their teaching. Successive training programs should allow practical exercises, cooperation with others and possible to try out new technologies closely related to learning.

2.3 Data-Driven Decision Making.

Data analytics will be critical in informing future education transformation since data is now increasingly becoming intertwined with education. The performance of student should be assessed; institutions should also identify areas that need to be strengthened and new initiatives that have been developed should also be assessed. School leaders should encourage the use of evidence in decision making processes.

3. Fostering a Culture of Collaboration

3.1 Importance of Collaborative Cultures

It emerging from the literature review that facilitating organisational change requires collaborative cultures. It is more likely that success of implementation and sustaining change if the institutions involves educators, administrators and the community. DuFour and Eaker (2016) proved that collaborative practices improve teacher pique, increase students' achievements, and increase school effectiveness.

3.2 Developing of professional learning communities (PLCs).

Analogous change work for the future should center on the formation of Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) in schools. PLCs involve the exchange of effective strategies for practice, joint curriculum design, and problem solving at the teachers' level. So, focusing on the development of community mentality among educators, the schools can succeed in the maintenance of continuous increase of effectiveness and creativity.

3.3: Involve parents and the Whole society.

As a result of the case studies presented here, it is evident that parents as well as the wider community must be included in the change process, if the change is to be sustained. For school-based change to happen, educational leaders need to involve other stakeholders in the community such as; businesses, other organizations, and families to support change. Programs that involve parents in decision making on the strategies that need to be taken in order to enhance the schools performance will go along way in getting parents to be more involved.

4. Equity and Human Rights: Enhancing Priorities.

4.1 Race and Ethnicity in Education.

Future education development should put into consideration basic equality and diversity. Ladson-Billings's research in 2018 shows that this supports equity to eliminate Systemic issues for equal learning environment. It is about time institutions analyzed their policies, their procedures and their curricula to check whether they offer equal opportunities to students of all cultures.

4.2 ACCORDING to the cultural relevance theory.

Applying culturally relevant pedagogy as activities for the change of the future is among the most important things. Teachers require Education for Diversity to learn how to bridge culture and differences in the classrooms. Recommendations of how educators can create a welcoming school atmosphere include an appreciation of cultural differences among students.

4.3 Supporting Marginalized Students.

Schools require intervention programs for disadvantaged students in that Schools require intervention programs in order to support students in need, who include low income earners, disabled, and first language learners. Further attempts should be made to stress on the idea of providing additional aid. support services, and customized interventions to guarantee that every student has fair access to quality education.

5. Building Resilience and Capacity for Change.

5.1 Cultivating a Growth Mindset.

Educational means of building up organizational resilience as a means of preparing for change is a great concept. Looking at staff, the leaders should cultivate an organizational culture of learning where everybody gets to embrace the aspect of growth, change, and learning throughout his/her life. According to Dweck (2016) mindset development intervention enhances motivation, academic, and the general climate in learning institutions.

5.2 in a gradual manner.

Seeing The change process in phases are ideal as institutions adapt to change because it is gradual. Fluctuation or rapid changes cause creaming and skimming by the staff. This type of change process should be implemented step by step with reflection, feedback, and change if needed during the educational leaders' initiatives.

5.3 Monitoring and Evaluation of Change Programme.

If institutions were to improve their rate of change, then the institutions have to develop good monitoring and evaluation. It is within this frame of reference that the possibility of a systematic examination of change initiatives periodically can produce insight regarding their efficacy and further reveal essential adjustments which can be implemented. One of the transformations leaders should encourage, is to promote a reflective practice in education, in which educators are supported on identifying the effects of their practice and make analyze decisions.

6. Strategic planning: what's the problem?

6.1 Strategic Vision.

Who is guiding change is essential for navigating educational institutions as such a vision and clear goal are fundamental for success. Managers need to engage stakeholders in development of vision that reflects the mission of the institution and the core beliefs. According to Senge (2019), it is seen that while developing change, stakeholders are encouraged by a vision.

6.2 Long Term Planning And Sustenance

By extension, every future change initiative should factor in long-term planning and sustainability into the planning process. Educational leaders need to consider implications of the changes on different interest groups and advise others about utilization of resources. In this element, the planning needs to be formulating goals and outcomes which can be measured in the course of the strategic periods.

6.3 Engaging Stakeholders in Planning

Involving people in activities for designing change is advantageous in building their commitment to bring change. This approach should be used by educational leaders to have several viewpoints represented in a conversation including educators, students, parents, and

members in a community. Partnering can also help ensure people commit to change and feel that the change is part of what they own.

7. Stressing on CPD

7.1 The Role of Ongoing Learning

Education is a dynamic process, and thus there is a need to contemplate a constant professional development for increasing the workforce ability to achieve change. Therefore, the future endeavours should be directed toward to provide effective continuing professional development for teachers that will be interesting and pertinent to teachers' practice. Findings by Desimone (2017) point to the effect of duration of professional development and enhances instructional practices as well as student achievement.

7.2: models of professional development for collaboration

As such, it is recommended that educational institutions think seriously about adopting collaborative models of professional development. This could come as peer coaching, mentoring and collaborative workshops where learners can develop more learning intervention partnerships. Interactions with other educators can help diminish the individual and institutional isolation so that states and institutions can foster the professional development that educators need.

7.3 Feedback Mechanisms Integration

This paper argues that using feedback mechanisms in professional development can help make such efforts more effective. Again, it will be to the advantage of educational leaders to engage their teachers in discussions on their professional learning requirements and processes needed to improve their practices. Thus institutions will be able to address the needs of teacher training by developing unique training model in response to the views that are expressed by the teachers.

8. Implications for Policy and Governance.

8.1 Aligning Policies with Change Goals.

Change management strategies have to positively dovetail with educational policies. It is important therefore for leaders to ensure that policies that encourage best practice, equity and effectiveness in development of education are supported. Brunner (2018) has also noted that policy coordination with institutional initiatives is the key to developing effective support.

8.2 Models of Collaborative Governance.

The future change efforts should integrate multisectoral governance systems where people and organisations in the community have a chance to participate in the decisions made. Therefore, through establishment of advisory committees or mentioning

partnership the educational institution can involve community in its governance structure that can reflect its values and needs.

8.3 Ensuring Accountability.

In this case, accountability is an essential part of the change management success. The staff of educational institutions should be provided with certain expectations and requirements concerning their work; otherwise, it is impossible to distinguish who is responsible for what. Semi-formal supervision of how the systems are performing relative to the goals established also enhances accountabilities and continuous improvement.

Conclusion

This paper aims to discuss the potential of educational institutions in creating change with formal models and AI technologies. Change does not merely entail implementation of new strategies and policies; it involves eradicating the foundation and practicing a different way in organizations. Frameworks of the models provided by Lewin, Kotter and Fullan include a clear focus on leadership, communication and stakeholders. AI builds on these models through evidence-based analysis, implementation of different procedures and individualized training but there are threats such as privacy infringement, digital divide, and technology phobia. Recent literature does not provide real-life information on the applicability of AI in models of change frameworks. As such, future research should

step into this gap and bring innovation in education that is sustainable, equitable, and supports advanced technology.

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